

Human interaction and impact on amphibian and reptiles- a review

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SUMMARY

Ethno zoological studies can help in human population assessment influences on local animal species and in the improvement of feasible managing plans. Animals species both wild and farm are essential to human beings. But animal species are in risk due to human activities like prohibited hunting for ornamental purposes, food, medicines, tree, land, and industry. Economic loss as a result of herpetofauna elimination is an important step in understanding the significance of reptiles and amphibians. The exponential human population growth creates deleterious effect on the diversity as well as spreading in worldwide. Several high-quality species of the wild animal and plants are extinct or endangered.

Keywords: Amphibian, Reptiles, Ethnoherptile, Medicine, Fats

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INTRODUCTION

Human growth rate is very fast in this age (Bloom, 2011) and have adverse influences on the natural habitats. The natural habitats are wilting due to urbanization, agriculture growth and industrial development (Altaf *et al.*, 2013). The forest habitats have been changed into agriculture habitat from the thousands of years (Bouma and Droogers, 1998). The agricultural development has been in progress since 1990s (Pimentel *et al.*, 2004) and triggered a competition between fauna and humans (Henle *et al.*, 2008). While, strengthening of agriculture and the improved production of agricultural domains are prerequisite of this era, at the similar time the preservation of fauna and flora is also likewise vital. Humans have arrived nearly in all ecosystems and their role in protection cannot be neglected (Henle *et al.*, 2008).

Ruegg *et al.* (2006) perceived that diversity, and density of fauna is effected by climate variation and this variation has bad influences on fauna specifically on massive mammals. Many species being migrated about 26% to 72% (Sparks and Menzel, 2002). Human activities e.g. agriculture escalation, urbanization and industrialization are the main reason of greenhouse effect, climate change and the worldwide warming (Saino *et al.*, 2010). Research on smoke and its effects on earth began at early seventeenth century and the term acid rain was first described during 1950s. Some animal's species like better to live in urban habitats; while some favor to peri-urban habitats and other choose to stay in natural habitats. Degenerations

reduced the total area and raise the amount of edge (Altaf, 2016). Rais *et al.* (2015) accepted that reptiles and amphibians are the most ignored as well as less intentional group of wildlife in country of Pakistan.

According to researchers, the “Northern Areas of Pakistan” are located on the state boundary between the Palearctic and Oriental biogeographical empires. This mountainous region is at the crossroads of major mountain ranges, has massive altitudinal and environmental inclines, and is the focus of biodiversity conservation efforts. However, nothing is known about the amphibians and reptiles of this region. Investigators employ a variety of strategies to explain species distribution and ecology, conduct a main study of toad genetic diversity, and achieve “*Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*” accession (Ficetola *et al.*, 2010). Researchers directed a study about the usage of reptiles in healing and other purposes in Brazil and argue their consequences for preservation. All existing discussions, examination and reports provided the medicinal or magic/religious usage of reptile species (Alves and Rosa, 2007b; Alves *et al.*, 2007; Alves *et al.*, 2009a; Alves *et al.*, 2009b; Ferreira *et al.*, 2009; Alves *et al.*, 2010).

Researchers proposed about relationship between herpetofauna and humans in many aspects since primitive time frequent difficulties of living with the urbanizing world are being faced by these animals. It has become a big challenge for the herpetofauna conservation. Regardless of many studies on herpetofauna, few researches have effectively explored the relationship of herpetofauna with human being. Collaborative sessions with “local villagers” were made with a survey and a “snake rescue group” was introduced, in order to give the awareness and conventional procedures amongst common people (Boruah *et al.*, 2016).

Michael *et al.* (2014) offered his study in which it was revealed that main reason of reptile and amphibian global decline is agricultural strengthening, as well as concern about how best protection of biodiversity in product production lands and meet worldwide food requirements. Agri-environment schemes (AES) are set to endeavor about assimilating biodiversity conservation in agricultural lands.

Researchers affirmed the studies with the objective of carrying out documentation of the herptiles of “Cholistan Desert” and study its ecology. Since “2001 to 2003”, intended exertions have been made to noted and seen the amphibians and reptiles in several parts of “Cholistan Desert”. About, 44 species away from more than four thousand specimens have been collected and observed from the study area. “Pit-fall” traps and “Hand Picking” exhibited best “results”, among different collecting procedures implemented for these studies. The voucher specimens have been recorded which are currently in the care of the “Pakistan Museum of Natural History”, Islamabad (Baig and Masroor, 2008).

BIODIVERSITY

The variety of life in a given place is referred to as biodiversity. In contrast to the more specific word species diversity, the term biodiversity was created to emphasize the various types of differences that exist within and among organisms at various levels of organization. It refers to the total of a region's genes, species, and biomes (Roberts, 1997). Amphibians and reptiles are basic components of the Earth's biodiversity because they play vital roles in food chain like herbivores, predators and

prey along with terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Khan, 2006). Amphibians and reptiles are significant bio-indicators. They point out “climate change” and are found in a diversity of habitats throughout the “world” apart from some distant islands. The “diversity” and “richness” is related to some avian and mammalian species (Adil *et al.*, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021)

ETHNO-HERPETOLOGY

The “Ethnoherpetology” is a division of “ethnozoology” that observe the relations among cultures of human and reptiles and amphibians. Ethno zoological studies can help in human population assessment influences on local animal species and in the improvement of feasible managing plans. Therefore they are essential to conservancy efforts (Alves and Souto, 2015; Alves *et al.*, 2018; Adil *et al.*, 2019; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Noor and Haider, 2020; Altaf and Faiz, 2021; Ijaz and Faiz, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Kamal and Faiz, 2022).

The habitat likings of species must be studied to know the diversity, (Riem *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016). Species prefer somewhat or totally well populous habitats (Bateman and Fleming, 2012; Riem *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016) but few species of animals like better to live near the human populated areas (Saito and Koike, 2013). Several species are adversely effected by human activities; so that some species choose new environment to live (i.e. urban, rural and agriculture); while other species fallen or involved in endangered list (Recher, 1999).

Human has faced the major animal extinction in “65 million years” (Balmford *et al.*, 2003). Current world extinction rates for fauna and flora are probably up to 1000 times greater than the former rate in the fossil record (Baillie *et al.*, 2004). Vertebrate fauna are deteriorating at extremely high rates (Beebee and Griffiths, 2005). The versatile utilization of animal species i.e. as “art”, “tools”, as “food”, in “medicine”, “entertainment”, “magic”, “music”, “religion” and for “trade” is acknowledged since prehistoric (Kaplan *et al.*, 2000; Alves *et al.*, 2012; Ali, 2017a, b; Altaf *et al.*, 2017; Haider *et al.*, 2017; Hakeem *et al.*, 2017).

MEDICINAL USES OF HERPETOFAUNA

The herpetofauna have extensive use in medicine (Akhtar, 2021; Nazir, 2021; Habib, 2022), but there is not have of thorough data regarding the level of the field as well as its effect on the animals present (Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Altaf *et al.*, 2020). This is testified that stroking, petting, and playing with pet like vertebrates are health advantageous rehearse. These practices lower heartbeat and control stroke (Beetz *et al.*, 2012). Animal based products extracted from different animal species are utilized as folklore therapy and assessed about “8.7%” of the very important chemicals used in modern health care system (Santos-Fita *et al.*, 2009). Still, animal based products are ignored as compared to plant species (Alves and Rosa, 2005). Residents of the peri-urban regions are more based on living thing derived things because they have enough traditional knowledge of zoo therapies (Santos-Fita *et al.*, 2009). Animals species both wild and farm are essential to human beings. However, wild animal species are threatened by anthropogenic activities such as banned hunting for food, medicine, or decorative purposes, deforestation, agricultural expansion, urbanization,

and industrialization (Rômulo *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016; Altaf *et al.*, 2017; Altaf *et al.*, 2018).

Reptile's species are applied in traditional general drugs mostly. Their function in general practices is interrelated with therapeutic usage as well as inhibition of diseases has been documented in many cultural zones all over the globe. Justification from different sources has shown that people mistreated the meat, eggs, oil, blood, bones, skin, shells and different parts of herptiles to supply foodstuff and ornamental tool as well as mystical items for long time. Regardless of all these usages, the herpetofauna is still used for cultural and medicinal aims, along with day-today activities (Alves *et al.*, 2012; Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Altaf *et al.*, 2020).

Herptiles are known as very interesting and most important animal species (Khan, 1999; Alves and Rosa, 2007a; Hussain *et al.*, 2015). In a lot of cultures, different species of herptiles are applied in ethno medicine and folklore to cure diseases (Alves and Rosa, 2007a; Rômulo *et al.*, 2012). About "10,450 of reptiles" and "7,850 amphibian species" have been appeared (Uetz, 2016) worldwide. In Pakistan "195 species of reptiles" (Khan, 2006) have been known until now. Traditional application of fauna taxa to treat ailments in human and other animals have been reported in Pakistan so far, apart from few reports on ethnozoology or zootherapies (Haider *et al.*, 2017; Hakeem *et al.*, 2017; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017a; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017b; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017c; Rauf *et al.*, 2017)

ANTHROPOGENIC IMPACT ON HERPETOFAUNA DIVERSITY

Amphibians and reptiles are mainly focus matter to anthropogenic activities. However, their commercial value is hardly considered when examining the value of natural means impressions. Amphibians and reptiles are main components of environments assisting as predators and basic food sources for some species. Some reptiles have been considered as core species. Economic loss as a result of herpetofauna elimination is an important step in understanding the significance of reptiles and amphibians and their requirements for valuable reform. Most of the species are commercially very important. Due to lack of information about their masses the commercial values across regions can be difficult for reptiles and amphibians (Gibbons *et al.*, 2000; Davic and Welsh Jr, 2004; Dumont, 2005).

Growth rate of human population was very slow till 1960s. After that growth rate upgraded, now exceeded up to 7 billion. If the speed of human population growth remains persistent than the population in world could reach 9.3 billion in 2050 (Bloom, 2011). The exponential human population growth creates deleterious effect on the diversity as well as spreading in worldwide. Enlarged human populations need food, habitation and luxury things; to achieve the demands of urbanization, agriculture intensification, industrialization resulting in pollution growth (Bouma and Droogers, 1998).

For agricultural development, deforestation has been done for 10,000 years. Due to this several high-quality species of the wild animal and plants are extinct or endangered and various common species executed new habitats in the last periods of 20th century (Bouma *et al.*, 1998) (Newton, 2004; Purtauf *et al.*, 2005; Stoate *et al.*, 2009). Human beings are using land of wild animal and lived near or within the

terrain of wild animal and builds negative influence on herpetofauna (Şekercioğlu *et al.*, 2012).

Humanities benefit directly or indirectly from biodiversity. Its conservation is required to eliminate the threat of extinction. Bold actions should be done to verify biodiversity conservation and protection. Several anuran species live in different zones of Pakistan, although none have a complete topographical range. The threats faced by amphibian fauna vary by species. The biggest risks that toads and frogs face in Pakistan are rapid urbanisation and industry. The erroneous development of housing developments and industrial zones is destroying amphibian breeding habitats. Closing of water pools to keep mosquitos at bay in order to manage dengue and malaria has a negative impact on the amphibian population. Drainage discharge carrying hazardous chemicals heaves out into streams and water bodies, which is a major cause of population reduction in many parts of Pakistan near industrial zones. Anuran species involving *Euphlyctis cyanophlyctis*, *Musa Ornate*, *Fejevaryia syhadrensis*, *H. tigerinus* are very affected entities (Khan, 2006).

TRADITIONAL USES OF HERPETOFAUNA

Some nomadic snake attracter tribes are actively contributing to the extinction of reptile species. They make deals with wild animals, reptiles, and other creatures. They are often called as "sanyasies" and "Tapri-was," and they have posed a danger to the indigenous reptile population throughout Pakistan. They relentlessly seek many reptile species enticed by high prices while bringing back the fur of these populations. Furthermore, the parts of reptiles are in great demand in marketplaces, and folklore healers use them in research to cure a variety of general disorders (Khan, 2006).

Scincid (skinks) populations from the genera "*Ophiomorus*", "*Novoeumeces*", "*Mabuya*", and "*Eurylepis*" are needed in few places due to a high cost by "hakims." To establish a market grip, the animals are captured while still alive, dried in the sun, and sold at a premium price as "regmahi," a major element of recipes known as potent sex boosters. The fat of reptiles is supposed to have medicinal properties for many folk healer and is often employed in studies of "balms", "oil", and "*Uromastyx*" rigid regarded to have specific chemotherapeutics properties. In Pakistan, "*Hoplobatrachus tigerinus*" and "*Uromastyx hardwickii*" are commonly employed in research institutes and educational organizations. Reptiles are commonly employed to express anatomy and conduct physiological tests. "*Uromastyx hardwickii*" is found in burrows. (Khan, 2006; Altaf *et al.*, 2020).

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